

MAGNETO-DIELECTRIC COMPOSITES WITH FREQUENCY SELECTIVE SURFACE LAYERS

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SUMMARY

Frequency selective surface layers sandwiched polymer composites were designed with electromagnetic properties required for radio frequency applications. The objective of this work involves tailoring material properties for an application. Design tools and fabrication techniques were developed to meet this objective.

Keywords: magneto-dielectric, frequency selective surfaces, composites

BACKGROUND

Radio frequency materials are becoming increasingly important in several areas of research. These materials are termed magneto-dielectric due to their enhanced electric and magnetic properties. The ultimate goal of this research would be to design and fabricate a material with non-trivial permeability ($\mu_r \geq 2$); a permittivity that is not much larger, and preferably smaller, than the permeability; and very low loss. The design of these materials is aided by computer simulation tools; fabrication and characterization require novel techniques that include a layered geometry composite.

Materials Applications

An example of a possible application for this material is the improvement of antenna substrates. Past attempts involved using a high permittivity substrate for the antenna. However, this can result in highly concentrated fields around the high permittivity region, often resulting in a narrowband characteristics and low efficiency. Moreover, the high permittivity results in a low impedance, causing difficulty in impedance matching the antenna. As a replacement to these high dielectric materials, magneto-dielectric materials would have more moderate impedance while improving the bandwidth of the antenna [1-2].

Having the ability to choose the properties of the material to best fit the application would be beneficial for these applications. One possible method to achieve this design is through the use of composite materials. The purpose of this research is to develop a means to design and fabricate materials that would be useful for these applications.

Electromagnetic Properties

Permittivity is a physical quantity that describes how an electric field affects and is affected by a dielectric medium and is determined by the ability of a material to polarize in response to an applied electric field, and thereby to cancel, partially, the field inside the material [3-4]. Permittivity characterizes a material's ability to transmit (or "permit") an electric field. The complex permittivity can be represented by an imaginary and non-imaginary component as seen in the equation below

$$\epsilon = \epsilon' - i\epsilon''$$

where ϵ' is the dielectric constant and ϵ'' is the dielectric loss factor. The dielectric constant actually depends on temperature and frequency (when not lossless), and the dielectric loss factor measures the material's ability to absorb and store energy [3].

Magnetic permeability is the property that describes a material's ability to become magnetized. Therefore, high permeability materials will become more easily magnetized than those of lower permeability. The complex permeability can also be represented by an imaginary and non-imaginary component where μ' is the permeability and μ'' is the magnetic loss factor [3]:

$$\mu = \mu' - i\mu''$$

The loss must remain low, so that the material will not heat up. Materials that would be particularly useful for RF designers are ones with non-trivial permeability (e.g. $\mu_r \geq 2$), a permittivity that is not much larger, and preferably smaller, than the permeability, and very low loss.

DESIGN CONCEPT

Preliminary Related Work

Preliminary experimental work was focused on studying composites comprised of spherical ferrimagnetic inclusions. However, the permeability did not increase to the desired extent. In order to achieve the desired magnetic properties, the weight fraction required would have to be 40% or higher, as seen in Figures 1 and 2 below.

Figure 1. Permittivity (left) and dielectric loss factor (right) vs. frequency (MHz) for iron oxide polymer nanocomposites

Figure 2. Magnetic permeability (left) and magnetic loss factor (right) vs. frequency (MHz) for iron oxide polymer nanocomposites

This behavior can be attributed to the geometry of the inclusions, which does not allow for a large magnetization in the composite; therefore, the permeability is near unity and the material is non-magnetic. Moreover, the spherical ferrimagnetic particles used in this study have a demagnetization factor of 1/3, meaning that they must be very tightly packed in order to result in a significant increase in permeability. Not only would very high volume fractions result in brittle composites with magnetic particles that would be very difficult to disperse, but the weight of this composite would become not much less than using the ferrite in bulk. These difficulties prompted the motivation to progress towards a new geometry, a layered composite.

Frequency Selective Surfaces

A frequency selective surface (FSS) is a periodic array of conducting patches or aperture elements. The frequency-filtering property of the FSS comes from the planar periodic structure; the elements reflect the incident microwave for a specific frequency range [5].

Figure3. Framework of material design

An incident wave to the FSS layer will cause an induced current in each element, which act as either capacitors or inductors (depending on the shape). These currents result in a scattered magnetic/electric field. A sandwiched composite with alternating layers of FSS arrays can therefore result in an increased permittivity and permeability. These properties will depend on the shapes on the FSS arrays (as seen in Figure 3).

Furthermore, it is also possible to dope each polymer layer with appropriate constituents, and use these metallic arrays to bias the magnetic dopants. The novel aspect of this work lies in the fact that materials will be co-designed with the dopants affecting the properties at low frequencies while the FSS arrays enhancing properties at higher frequencies.

DESIGN RESULTS

The effects of variation in FSS element shape, size, periodicity, and dielectric layer thickness on the resulting properties of interest – permittivity and permeability – were the primary focus of initial simulations. Ansoft Designer was used for simulation of the composites. The output from Ansoft Designer was the reflection and transmission data; an extraction routine was written to extract the electromagnetic properties.

For a slab of finite thickness, d , reflection and transmission coefficients for a normally incident plane wave can be represented with S parameters, S_{11} and S_{21} . The impedance, η , is related to the effective permeability and permittivity (μ and ϵ) of the slab material. The wave number, k , in the equations below is related to the plane wave characteristics, frequency (f), and the slab material properties. See the equations below [3].

$$\eta = \sqrt{\frac{\mu}{\epsilon}} \quad k = 2\pi f \sqrt{\epsilon\mu}$$

$$S_{11} = \frac{(\eta^2 - 1)(1 - e^{-2jkd})}{(\eta + 1)^2 - e^{-2jkd}(\eta - 1)^2}$$

$$S_{21} = \frac{4\eta e^{-jkd}}{(\eta + 1)^2 - e^{-2jkd}(\eta - 1)^2}$$

For a simple slab of polyethylene with a normally incident plane wave, the reflection and transmission data was calculated.

Figure 4. Transmission (dB) vs. frequency (GHz) for varying slab thickness

For a simple slab of polyethylene, the transmission power remains near 1 for this range of frequencies; moreover, the effective permittivity and permeability remain constant at 2.2 and 1, respectively (with low loss). By implementing the frequency selective surfaces in the polyethylene slab, the reflection and transmission data can be tailored to resonate at the desired range of frequencies. This change in the reflection and transmission spectrum will result in enhanced permittivity and permeability for the composite.

Square Loop Elements Analysis

For initial simulations, the square loop (A in Figure3) was chosen because of its simplicity. The purpose of this investigation was to note the effects of changing the size, periodicity, and dielectric (polymer) layer thickness. For these first cases, a one layer FSS sandwiched composite was designed with polyethylene as the polymer and silver as the FSS element material (Figure 5).

Figure 5. Square loop element and sandwiched composite design concept

The layered geometry was created in Ansoft Designer, with a unit cell representing the infinite FSS array layer. A normal incidence for the incoming plane wave was chosen for these simulations. The length of the square loop will affect where the transmission or reflection will resonate. For example, for the resonance to occur at 3 GHz, the length of the square should be approximately $\lambda/4$, or 3.3cm. This fact can be noted in Figure 6. For each case here, the polymer layer thickness was held constant at 1.5 cm.

The transmission and reflection data was used to extract the dielectric and magnetic properties (real and imaginary). Already with one layer of square loop elements, it can be seen that the magnetic permeability (μ') is enhanced for different bandwidths for the varying size square loops, ranging from 1.2 to 1.8.

Figure 6. Transmission (dB) vs. frequency (GHz) for square loop elements

The polymer layers that form the FSS sandwiched composite allow for an increase in bandwidth; however, the thickness of the polymer layers will affect the properties of the composite.

Figure 7. Permittivity and permeability (ϵ and μ) vs. frequency (GHz)

For previous cases shown above, the thickness of each layer was 1.5cm. By increasing the thickness of the polymer layers, the bandwidth is increased and the resonant frequency is shifted. Figure 7 shows a sample of the permittivity and permeability for a case with the polymer thickness of 2cm. Permeability is enhanced over this range of

frequencies, although still below 2. Periodicity affects the resonance of the transmission and reflection data; moreover, the bandwidth will be increased for the shorter periods.

Slot Arrays - Elements Analysis

Two common FSS arrays used in several applications are dipole and slot arrays. Figure 8 shows the slot array and the slot (single element); similarly, the dipole array would be arranged with dipoles (the metal would replace where the etched area is).

Figure 8. FSS slot array and single FSS slot element (with labeled dimensions)

The main difference between these cases is that the electric currents are excited with the dipoles, and the “magnetic currents” are excited with slots. Since permeability is difficult to enhance with particles added to the polymer, the FSS slot array may improve the permeability for the composite.

A 1-layer FSS composite was simulated with the FSS layer composed of slot elements ($L = 3\text{cm}$, $W = 1\text{cm}$) with the unit cell ($A = 3.5\text{cm}$, $B = 1.5\text{cm}$), again with silver as the element material and polyethylene as the polymer layers. The thickness of the polymer layers was again varied, and Figure 9 shows the results for these cases.

Figure 9. Transmission (dB) vs. frequency (GHz) for FSS slot array composite

Figure 10. μ' vs. frequency (GHz) for FSS slot array composite

The slot arrays do improve the permeability to the extent required for the applications of interest; however, the permeability is quite low and in some cases negative for these cases. In order to improve this property, composites can be fabricated with inclusions in the polymer layers that will result in a higher dielectric property polymer.

Figure 11. Permittivity and permeability (ϵ and μ) vs. frequency (GHz)

To simulate this situation, a case was simulated with the polymer layer material having a dielectric property of 5 and permeability of 1, with the slot array FSS layer (slot size: $L = 3\text{cm}$, $W = 1\text{cm}$ and unit cell size: $A = 3.5\text{cm}$, $B = 1.5\text{cm}$). The polymer layer

thickness was 0.5 cm each. Figure 11 above shows the permeability and permittivity vs. frequency (GHz) for this case.

Also, by adding more than one FSS layer to the polymer, to form a multi-layer FSS composite, the properties can be further enhanced. By adding a second FSS layer with the same periodicity and shape dimension, the bandwidth will be increased. The same size slots and unit cells were used for this case, and the polymer layer thickness was again 0.5cm; since there were two FSS layers sandwiched for the composite, 3 polymer layers were used. Figure 12 shows the results for this.

Figure 12. Permittivity and permeability (ϵ and μ) vs. frequency for 2 layer FSS sandwiched composite

FABRICATION EFFORTS

Synthesis techniques have been developed to fabricate FSS layered composites once designed. This method includes first coating thin polyethylene films with the metal of choice (i.e. silver) using sputter coating, then transferring the patterns for the FSS arrays using a photolithography technique, and finally layering the films using epoxy as a “glue” and curing the composite using conventional oven cure or compression molding. The benefit of using epoxy as the polymer matrix can be noted when curing layer by layer, with compression molding or oven cure. Photolithography has been used in the past to create patterns for frequency selective surfaces. Steps involve coating the film with photoresist and using a photomask to transfer the pattern of choice while exposed to UV light. The unwanted silver sections are then etched away with a silver etchant, and the remaining photoresist is removed with a stripping solution.

The frequency selective layers were etched on a polymer substrate. Polyethylene films (~125 μm thick) have been coated with silver (~100 nm thick layer). Photolithography has been used to pattern the silver coated polymer films. Similar geometries to those simulated previously will be fabricated with compression molding or a layer by layer thermal curing process. The electromagnetic properties of these samples will be

analyzed to compare to theoretical results shown previously. Below (Figure 13) is an example of etched square loops using the silver coated polyethylene film and the photolithography process.

Figure 13. Etched FSS surface (left: square loops, right: square loop slots)

FUTURE AND ONGOING WORK

FSS sandwiched polymer composites have been successfully designed to meet the originally set goal: non-trivial permeability ($\mu_r > 2$), a permittivity that is not much larger, and preferably smaller, than the permeability, and very low loss for frequencies greater than 2GHz. Current work will focus on optimizing the design to maximize bandwidth over which the properties will remain enhanced. Moreover, fabrication efforts have begun to verify the design outcomes described earlier. Characterization will involve measuring the reflection and transmission through the material and extracting the permittivity and permeability.

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